

Adapting to Climate Variability: The Role of Environmental Factors in Crop Yield Stability in Türkiye

Muhammed BENLİ^{1*}

¹ Bilecik Seyh Edebali University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, Department of Economics, Bilecik

*Corresponding author: muhammed.benli@bilecik.edu.tr

Abstract

This study examines the effects of key climatic factors—temperature, precipitation, and atmospheric CO₂—on the yields of two crops in Türkiye: barley and peas. Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing methodology with time series data from 1981 to 2020, we investigate both short-term and long-term relationships between these environmental variables and crop yields. Our findings reveal that barley yields exhibit a cointegration relationship with climatic factors, indicating a stable long-term equilibrium, while pea shows no such enduring association, suggesting it is more sensitive to short-term fluctuations. The results underscore the resilience of barley in adapting to sustained environmental changes, contrasting with the immediate but transient responses observed for peas. These findings have important implications for agricultural management and policy, particularly in addressing crop-specific adaptation strategies under increasing climatic variability. Policies focused on enhancing soil health, optimizing irrigation, and promoting climate-resilient crop varieties could help bolster food security and agricultural sustainability in Türkiye. Future research could further explore adaptive measures and examine other region-specific variables that might influence crop yield dynamics in the context of a changing climate.

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1. Introduction

Agriculture plays a central role in Türkiye's economy, significantly contributing to rural livelihoods, food security, employment, and overall economic stability. However, agricultural productivity is closely linked to climatic variables, making this sector particularly vulnerable to climate change and environmental variability (Deressa et al., 2005; Dumrul and Kilicaslan, 2017). In particular, critical climatic factors such as temperature, precipitation, and atmospheric CO₂ have substantial impacts on crop growth, yield quantity, and product quality (Neenu et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2019). With ongoing global climate trends leading to rising temperatures, shifting precipitation patterns, and increasing atmospheric CO₂ levels, assessing their impacts on agricultural productivity is essential for developing appropriate adaptation strategies to sustain agricultural output and safeguard food security in Türkiye.

Türkiye's agricultural sector is characterized by diverse agroecological zones, each hosting distinct climatic conditions and crop systems (Muminjanov and Karagöz, 2018). This diversity highlights the necessity of crop-specific analyses rather than generalized evaluations of climate impacts. Barley and peas represent two economically and nutritionally important crops with distinct climate sensitivities, making them ideal candidates for understanding how climate variability affects agricultural productivity differently across crop types. Barley, a cereal crop extensively cultivated in Türkiye, tends to be relatively resilient to climate fluctuations, mainly due to its deeper rooting systems and physiological adaptability to temperature and moisture changes (Olgun et al., 2013). Conversely, peas, although economically valuable and nutritionally beneficial, typically display greater sensitivity to short-term climatic disturbances, such as sudden shifts in temperature and irregular water availability (Allen and de Brauw, 2019). Despite recognizing these general crop characteristics, the literature lacks sufficient empirical evidence to clarify precisely how these crops

respond differently to climatic conditions over both short and long terms, leaving policymakers and agricultural managers without targeted guidelines for climate adaptation.

The complexity of crop yield responses to climatic variability necessitates detailed, crop-specific investigations. Rising temperatures can positively influence plant growth rates initially but might also shorten growth cycles, reducing potential yields (Peiris et al., 1996; Zhu et al., 2021; Bernacchi et al., 2023). Changes in precipitation patterns affect soil moisture availability, nutrient dynamics, and plant water stress, with extremes such as droughts and floods significantly affecting yield stability (Abou Seeda and Zaghoul, 2022; Jackson et al., 2023; Furtak and Wolińska, 2023). Similarly, elevated CO₂ concentrations may initially enhance growth in C3 plants, yet prolonged exposure—particularly in combination with water or nutrient deficiencies—could become detrimental, limiting crop productivity over time (Kirschbaum, 2004; Brouder and Volenec, 2008; Boretti and Florentine, 2019). Given these complexities, examining specific climatic factors in relation to crop physiology and agronomic characteristics is critical for effectively managing climate risks and improving resilience.

To address these issues comprehensively, this study applies the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach, an econometric methodology particularly suitable for time series analysis when variables have mixed integration orders. This technique enables the simultaneous examination of both short-run fluctuations and long-term equilibrium relationships between crop yields and climatic variables, offering detailed insights into crop-specific responses. In this context, distinguishing crops exhibiting stable, long-term adaptations to climate changes from those primarily affected by short-term environmental variability becomes fundamental for tailoring adaptation strategies. Such differentiation is crucial because crops responding positively to long-term climatic

shifts might benefit from sustained agronomic interventions, whereas crops sensitive to immediate climatic disturbances require adaptive short-term management practices.

Ultimately, this study seeks to clarify precisely how key climatic factors—temperature, precipitation, and CO₂—affect barley and pea yields in Türkiye, contributing valuable empirical evidence to inform agricultural policy and practice. The findings have direct policy implications, potentially guiding strategic decisions such as long-term investments in soil health, breeding of resilient crop varieties, or short-term adaptive techniques like improved irrigation scheduling and dynamic planting calendars. By providing an explicit and crop-specific assessment, this study significantly advances the understanding of agricultural resilience and supports the

development of informed adaptation measures essential for ensuring agricultural sustainability and food security in Türkiye amid increasing climatic uncertainty.

2. Material and Methods

This study examines the impact of critical climatic factors—temperature, precipitation, and atmospheric CO₂—on the yields of two crops in Türkiye: barley and peas. We utilize the ARDL bounds testing methodology with time series data from 1981 to 2020. All series are transformed into their natural logarithmic forms, enabling the interpretation of the estimated coefficients as elasticities. Table 1 presents summary information regarding the data utilized in the analyses, while Table 2 offers the descriptive statistics of the series.

Table 1. Summary of the variables

Target variable	Proxy variable	Symbol	Definiton	Source
Crop yield	Crop yields	YIELD	Yields are measured in tonnes per hectare	Our World in Data
Temperature	Surface temperature	TEMP	Average annual surface temperature. The temperature of the air measured 2 meters above the ground, encompassing land, sea, and in-land water surfaces.	Our World in Data
Precipitation	Precipitation	PREC	Annual precipitation per unit area (mm)	Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change
Carbon Emissions	CO ₂ emissions	CO2	CO ₂ emissions from fossil fuels and industry. Land-use change is not included.	Our World in Data

We examine the short-run and long-run relationships between crop yields and environmental factors using an ARDL modeling framework. The ARDL approach allows for the evaluation of whether each crop yield exhibits a cointegration relationship with climatic variables, signifying a stable long-term dependency, or if it is primarily affected by short-term variations. The ARDL model was chosen for its adaptability in managing

variables integrated of varying orders, I(0) or I(1), rendering it appropriate for our dataset. The ARDL approach, in contrast to conventional cointegration methods, does not necessitate that all variables be integrated at the same order (Pesaran et al., 2001; Kripfganz and Schneider, 2023). We individually estimate each model for each crop to discern crop-specific correlations with temperature, precipitation, and CO₂.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics

Variables	No. of obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
BARLEY	40	2.309	0.318	1.351	2.936	-0.188	3.675
PEA	40	2.497	0.314	1.818	3.059	-0.362	2.226
TEMP	40	11.404	0.889	9.256	13.329	0.118	2.945
PREC	40	577.85	65.157	445.000	717.000	0.066	2.574
CO2	40	240 m	108 m	79.2 m	431 m	0.250	1.841
ln _BARLEY	40	0.827	0.145	0.300	1.077	-0.892	5.649
ln _PEA	40	0.907	0.131	0.598	1.118	-0.581	2.510
ln _TEMP	40	2.431	0.078	2.225	2.590	-0.112	3.058
ln _PREC	40	6.353	0.114	6.098	6.575	-0.191	2.537
ln _CO2	40	19.186	0.495	18.187	19.881	-0.370	2.078

Source: Author's calculations

The general ARDL ($p, q1, q2, q3$) model for a crop yield can be specified as follows

$$\Delta YIELD_t = \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i \Delta YIELD_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^{q1} \beta_j \Delta TEMP_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^{q2} \gamma_k \Delta PREC_{t-k} + \sum_{l=0}^{q3} \delta_l \Delta CO2_{t-l} + \theta ECT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

where $YIELD_t$ is the log-transformed yield for each crop in year t ; $TEMP_t$, $PREC_t$, and $CO2_t$ represent the log-transformed temperature, precipitation, and CO_2 levels, respectively. ECT_{t-1} denotes the error correction term obtained from the cointegration relationship, signifying the long-term equilibrium association for crops exhibiting cointegration, while ε_t is the error term.

We also include interaction terms ($TEMP \times PREC$, $TEMP \times CO2$, and $PREC \times CO2$) as additional control variables in each crop's ARDL model to elucidate the synergistic effects of climate variables. To assess the presence of a long-run relationship, we conduct the following steps:

- Before estimation, we assess the stationarity of each variable utilizing the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests. This step verifies that none of the variables are integrated of order 2 or higher ($I(2)$), since the ARDL methodology is only suitable for variables that are $I(0)$ or $I(1)$ (Pesaran et al., 2001).

- We employ the ARDL bounds testing method for each crop to examine the existence of a long-term relationship between yield and climatic variables. The F-statistic from the bounds test is evaluated against critical values to ascertain the presence of cointegration (Kripfganz and Schneider, 2023):

- If the F-statistic exceeds the upper bound, we conclude that a long-run relationship exists.
- If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we conclude that no long-run relationship exists.

- If the F-statistic falls between the bounds, the result is inconclusive.

- For crops exhibiting cointegration, we estimate an error correction model (ECM) to elucidate both short-term and long-term dynamics. The ECM incorporates an error correction term (ECT_{t-1}) that quantifies the rate at which the yield realigns with deviations from the long-term equilibrium. A substantial error correction term with a negative coefficient signifies that yields revert to equilibrium after transient fluctuations.

- For crops without cointegration, we concentrate on the short-run coefficients obtained from the differenced terms in the

ARDL model. These coefficients reflect the immediate impact of variations in temperature, precipitation, and CO₂ on yield, without assuming any sustained relationship over time.

3. Results and Discussion

This section presents the empirical findings of our analysis, emphasizing the relationships between environmental variables and crop yields (barley and peas). We summarize the findings of the ARDL modeling approach, highlighting the existence of cointegration for certain crop and the ramifications of the estimated short-run coefficients for the crops. The analysis is organized to highlight the long-term relationships for each crop, subsequent to the examination of the short-term dynamics. A point that will be examined in detail in a subsequent section is essential to note here. Our analysis reveals a cointegration relationship for barley, indicating a stable long-term equilibrium between crop yield and the explanatory variables (temperature, precipitation, and CO₂ levels). This discovery demonstrates that these factors exert a lasting influence on barley yield over time. Thus, we analyze both the short-run and long-run coefficients for this crop, assessing its immediate reactions to environmental changes

as well as its long-term adaptations. The long-term coefficients indicate the persistent impact of these variables on crop yield, whereas the short-term coefficients represent the immediate reactions to climate variability. Conversely, for peas, there is no evidence of cointegration, indicating that the peas yield does not exhibit a stable long-term relationship with the explanatory variables examined in this study. Consequently, we concentrate solely on the short-term dynamics of this crop. Analyzing the short-run coefficients reveals the immediate and potentially volatile reactions of this crops to variations in temperature, precipitation, and CO₂, highlighting its sensitivity to short-term environmental fluctuations rather than any enduring, long-term adjustment trajectory. The differentiation between crops exhibiting a cointegration relationship and those that do not offers significant insights into their respective responses to climatic conditions, informing adaptive management practices customized to each crop's unique yield behavior in the face of environmental change. Prior to estimating the ARDL, it is imperative to confirm that the variables exhibit stationarity. The outcomes of the ADF and PP tests are displayed in Table 3. The results indicate that none of the variables are integrated at the second order.

Table 3. Unit root tests

Variable	ADF		PP	
	C	C/T	C	C/T
CO _{2t}	-2.508(0)	-2.033(0)	-3.977(11)***	-1.618(8)
ΔCO _{2t}	-6.098(0)***	-6.713(0)***	-6.100(2)***	-7.937(9)***
TEMP _t	-0.712(1)	-7.078(0)***	-0.757(8)	-7.317(6)***
ΔTEMP _t	-10.869(0)***	-5.910(3)***	-26.691(16)***	-28.363(15)***
PRECIP _t	-6.829(0)***	-6.768(0)***	-10.020(22)***	-11.642(26)***
ΔPRECIP _t	-6.968(1)***	-6.855(1)***	-26.624(22)***	-28.496(21)***
PEA _t	-2.155(0)	-3.571(0)**	-2.089(1)	-3.646(2)**
ΔPEA _t	-7.755(0)***	-7.671(0)***	-8.465(4)***	-8.504(4)***
BARLEY _t	-1.813(1)	-7.506(0)***	-3.424(3)**	-17.419(30)***
ΔBARLEY _t	-11.503(0)***	-11.345(0)***	-33.157(23)***	-33.078(23)***
TEMP × PREC	-6.710(0)***	-6.819(0)***	-7.263(11)***	-11.704(22)***
Δ(TEMP × PREC)	-6.981(1)***	-6.866(1)***	-26.891(23)***	-30.375(22)***
TEMP × CO ₂	-2.408(0)	-1.823(0)	-4.041(8)***	-1.364(7)
Δ(TEMP × CO ₂)	-5.992(0)***	-6.682(0)***	-5.992(1)***	-7.181(6)***
PREC × CO ₂	-2.896(0)*	-6.136(0)***	-2.701(1)*	-6.279(7)***
Δ(PREC × CO ₂)	-6.755(1)***	-6.682(1)***	-20.343(29)***	-28.999(23)***

Note: The lag lengths (given in parentheses) for the ADF test determined by the SIC and the appropriate bandwidths for the PP test determined by the Newey-West Bandwidth. *** p<0.01, ** 0.01<p<0.05, * 0.05<p<0.10

The empirical findings from the ARDL analysis for barley yield in Turkiye reveal both long-run and short-run relationships with climatic variables. The analysis is based on the optimal lag length determined by the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) for the model and the resulting coefficients from the ECM. The AIC is widely preferred in ARDL modeling due to its effectiveness in balancing model complexity and goodness-of-fit, thereby minimizing the loss of information while avoiding over-parameterization. Compared to other

criteria, such as the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) or Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC), AIC tends to perform better in relatively smaller samples, such as ours (1981-2020), by avoiding overly restrictive model specifications that could exclude relevant dynamics. Therefore, utilizing the AIC provides robust and reliable lag lengths, ensuring that our ARDL estimates adequately capture both short-run and long-run relationships between climatic variables and crop yields. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. ARDL results (barley)

Model: $F(\text{BARLEY}_t / \text{TEMP}_t, \text{PREC}_t, \text{CO2}_t, \text{TEMP} \times \text{PREC}_t, \text{TEMP} \times \text{CO2}_t, \text{PREC} \times \text{CO2}_t)$			
Optimal lag length: (2, 2, 1, 2, 2, 2, 2)		F-stat: 9.727***	
Significance level		Critical values	
		Lower bound	Upper bound
% 1		3.800	5.643
% 5		2.797	4.211
% 10		2.353	3.599
Error correction model			
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-stat
C	-6496.288***	829.765	-7.829
$\Delta \text{BARLEY}_{t-1}$	-0.296***	0.105	-2.831
ΔTEMP_t	397.167**	168.180	2.362
ΔTEMP_{t-1}	-568.757***	150.163	-3.788
ΔPREC_t	474.473***	165.853	2.861
ΔCO2_t	-78.253*	45.114	-1.735
ΔCO2_{t-1}	-134.181***	38.241	-3.509
$\Delta \text{TEMP} \times \text{PREC}_t$	-100.600***	35.012	-2.873
$\Delta \text{TEMP} \times \text{PREC}_{t-1}$	5.3506***	0.918	5.826
$\Delta \text{TEMP} \times \text{CO2}_t$	12.804	8.278	1.547
$\Delta \text{TEMP} \times \text{CO2}_{t-1}$	28.092***	7.670	3.663
$\Delta \text{PREC} \times \text{CO2}_t$	2.045***	0.696	2.937
$\Delta \text{PREC} \times \text{CO2}_{t-1}$	-1.422***	0.245	-5.811
ECT_{t-1}	-1.176***	0.150	-7.829
Long-run coefficients			
TEMP	1222.105**	543.333	2.249
PREC	879.794**	386.446	2.277
CO2	-40.101*	19.377	-2.069
TEMP \times PREC	-194.496**	82.920	-2.346
TEMP \times CO2	0.594	3.642	0.163
PREC \times CO2	5.880***	2.044	2.877
Diagnostic tests			
χ^2_{SER}	1.283 (0.304)	R^2	0.881
χ^2_{HET}	0.743 (0.713)	R^2_{Adj}	0.756
χ^2_{NORM}	0.780 (0.677)	F_{ist}	7.031 (0.000)
χ^2_{RAMSEY}	0.721 (0.408)	Cusum	Stable
DW	1.431	Cusum(sqr)	Stable

Note: Probability values in parentheses. χ^2_{SER} , χ^2_{HET} , χ^2_{NORM} , χ^2_{RAMSEY} denote the Breusch-Godfrey LM autocorrelation, Breusch-Pagan heteroscedasticity, Jarque-Bera normality, and model specification error test statistics, respectively. Cusum and Cusum of squares (sqr) represent the stability test statistics. Given the small sample size, the bounds test critical values are from Narayan (2005): Case III- unrestricted intercept and no trend *** p<0.01, ** 0.01< p<0.05, * 0.05< p<0.10.

The F-statistic for the bounds test is 9.727, which is significant at the 1% level, indicating the presence of cointegration among the yield of barley and the climatic factors. This confirms that there is a stable long-term relationship between wheat yield and the selected climatic variables. The ARDL results for barley yield analysis show how environmental factors (temperature, precipitation, and CO₂) along with their interactions affect barley production in Türkiye in both short-run and long-run contexts.

The ECT, with a highly significant coefficient of -1.176, indicates a rapid adjustment towards equilibrium. This means that approximately 117.6% of the deviation from long-run equilibrium is corrected each period, suggesting a quick return to stability after short-term shocks in barley yield.

The significant negative coefficient of the lagged barley yield suggests an inverse relationship with the previous period's yield. A high yield in the preceding period seems to correlate with a lower yield in the current period, which might indicate depletion of soil nutrients or other residual effects that temporarily limit yield capacity following a high-yield period.

TEMP has mixed effects in the short run. The coefficient for current temperature (397.167) is positive and significant, indicating that a rise in temperature has an immediate positive impact on barley yield in the short run. This suggests that moderate temperature increases during certain stages of barley growth, such as germination and vegetative growth, may be beneficial by accelerating physiological processes and potentially extending the growing season (Zhu et al., 2021). The coefficient for lagged temperature (-568.757) is negative and significant, suggesting that prolonged higher temperatures negatively affect barley yield. This adverse effect could be due to accumulated heat stress, which can harm

barley's reproductive phases, leading to reduced grain filling and ultimately lowering yield (Jacott and Boden, 2020). The contrasting effects of current versus lagged temperature highlight the importance of maintaining optimal temperature ranges, as sustained high temperatures can become detrimental.

The coefficient for current precipitation is positive and significant (474.473), indicating that increased precipitation in the short term benefits barley yield. Adequate soil moisture from rainfall supports barley's growth by facilitating nutrient uptake and maintaining cell turgor, particularly beneficial in regions with limited irrigation resources (Metwally and Pollard, 1959; Day et al., 1978; Day et al., 1981). However, there is no lagged precipitation term in this model, implying that only immediate precipitation changes are significant for barley yield in the short run.

The coefficient for current CO₂ is negative and marginally significant (-78.253), suggesting that an immediate increase in CO₂ may have a slight negative impact on barley yield in the short run. While CO₂ can enhance growth in some C3 crops, high levels may stress barley if not balanced with other factors. The negative and significant lagged coefficient (-134.181) suggests that prolonged exposure to high CO₂ levels has a more substantial negative effect on barley yield. This could reflect cumulative physiological stress or soil nutrient depletion associated with sustained high CO₂ levels, which may disrupt growth conditions over time.

The interaction terms reveal complex dynamics between temperature, precipitation, and CO₂, illustrating how combinations of these factors influence barley yield in unique ways. The current interaction between temperature and precipitation is negative and significant (-100.600), suggesting that simultaneous increases in temperature and precipitation

may harm barley yield in the short run. This adverse effect might occur due to overly humid conditions or heightened susceptibility to diseases, which are exacerbated by high temperatures (Hakala et al., 2012). The lagged $TEMP \times PREC$ interaction is positive and highly significant (5.3506), indicating that past balanced temperature and precipitation conditions foster favorable growing conditions in the current period. This delayed positive effect may be due to residual moisture benefits or improved soil conditions following moderate warmth and rainfall (Jackson et al., 2023).

The immediate $TEMP \times CO_2$ interaction term (12.804) is positive but not statistically significant, indicating that current combined changes in temperature and CO_2 do not have a strong effect on barley yield. The lagged $TEMP \times CO_2$ term is positive and significant (28.092), suggesting that sustained exposure to high CO_2 levels, combined with moderate temperature increases, positively impacts yield (Gardi et al., 2022). This interaction might enhance photosynthesis and increase crop resilience to temperature changes, reflecting CO_2 's potential to improve barley's heat tolerance over time.

The current $PREC \times CO_2$ interaction coefficient (2.045) is positive and significant, indicating that combined increases in precipitation and CO_2 have a favorable effect on barley yield in the short run. This result might be due to the synergistic effect of moisture and CO_2 , enhancing nutrient uptake and photosynthesis (Shanker et al., 2022). The lagged $PREC \times CO_2$ term is negative and highly significant (-1.422), suggesting that prolonged high levels of both precipitation and CO_2 can negatively impact barley yield. This adverse effect might stem from nutrient leaching or imbalanced soil conditions when moisture is excessive

under elevated CO_2 conditions, ultimately reducing yield potential.

On the other hand, the long-run coefficients show the persistent effects of surface temperature, precipitation, CO_2 levels, and their interactions on barley yield over time. Unlike short-run dynamics, these long-run results reflect sustained impacts that may inform broader agricultural and environmental strategies for barley production. The positive and significant coefficient for temperature indicates that, in the long run, increased temperatures contribute positively to barley yield. This suggests that, over time, barley may benefit from warmer temperatures, possibly through longer growing seasons or through varieties that can thrive in slightly warmer conditions (Martin et al., 2017). This result implies that moderate temperature increases could enhance barley growth and yield resilience in the long term, provided they remain within a favorable range.

The positive and significant coefficient for precipitation implies that sustained increases in rainfall positively impact barley yield in the long run. Consistent moisture availability supports soil hydration, which is essential for nutrient uptake and healthy growth in barley, especially in rain-fed agricultural systems (Metwally and Pollard, 1959; Rodriguez et al., 2024). The significance of this effect indicates that adequate precipitation is crucial to maintaining and potentially improving barley yield over extended periods.

The negative and marginally significant effect of CO_2 suggests that sustained high CO_2 levels may reduce barley yield in the long run. While CO_2 often enhances crop growth initially through its fertilization effect, long-term increases may impose indirect stress, possibly due to accompanying environmental changes like higher temperatures or soil degradation.

This finding implies that while CO₂ might initially boost yields, its long-term impact may be detrimental, highlighting the complexity of CO₂'s role in barley production (Gardi et al., 2022).

The interaction terms reveal how the combined influence of temperature, precipitation, and CO₂ affects barley yield in the long term, highlighting conditions where these factors may complement or counterbalance each other. The negative and significant coefficient for TEMP × PREC suggests that, over time, simultaneous increases in both temperature and precipitation may reduce barley yield. This could occur because high temperatures combined with high moisture can create overly humid conditions, promoting diseases or other stresses that reduce crop productivity (Weaver, 1943). This finding underscores the need for balanced environmental conditions, as extreme or simultaneous increases in temperature and moisture may exceed optimal growth conditions.

The positive but insignificant coefficient for TEMP × CO₂ suggests that the long-term combined effect of temperature and CO₂ does not strongly impact barley yield. This result may indicate that CO₂ levels, when interacting with temperature over extended periods, do not significantly alter the effects of temperature on barley, and thus CO₂ may not be a major factor in mitigating temperature-related stress in the long term. The positive and highly significant coefficient for PREC × CO₂ indicates that long-term increases in both precipitation and CO₂ positively impact barley yield. This interaction effect may result from enhanced photosynthetic activity and nutrient uptake under elevated CO₂ levels, combined with sufficient soil moisture, creating favorable growth

conditions. The significance of this result suggests that, in the long run, stable precipitation along with elevated CO₂ levels can support barley resilience and yield.

Moreover, the diagnostic tests affirm the robustness of the model. Breusch-Godfrey and Breusch-Pagan tests confirm no issues with autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity, suggesting that the model's residuals are well-behaved and the coefficients are reliable. Normality test (Jarque-Bera) confirms that residuals follow a normal distribution, which supports the statistical validity of the results. Finally, model stability tests (CUSUM and CUSUM of squares tests) show that the model is stable, indicating that the estimated parameters are consistent over time.

In contrast, the empirical findings from the ARDL analysis of pea yield indicate that there is no evidence of cointegration with climatic variables, suggesting the absence of a stable long-term equilibrium relationship. The analysis is based on the optimal lag length determined by the AIC for the model and the resulting coefficients from the ECM. The results are summarized in Table 5.

The results for peas indicate there is no cointegration, as the F-statistic (2.631) does not exceed the critical upper bound values. This lack of cointegration means there is no stable, long-term equilibrium relationship between the environmental variables (temperature, precipitation, CO₂) and pea yields.

Without a long-term relationship, the interpretation focuses exclusively on short-run dynamics. This means that any changes in temperature, precipitation, or CO₂ levels may temporarily impact pea yields, but these effects are not sustained over time.

Table 5. ARDL results (pea)

Model: F(PEA/ TEMP _t , PREC _t , CO2 _t , TEMP × PREC _t , TEMP × CO2 _t , PREC × CO2 _t)			
Optimal Lag Length: (1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 0, 1)		F-stat: 2.631	
Significance Level		Critical Values	
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
%1		3.800	5.643
%5		2.797	4.211
%10		2.353	3.599
Error Correction Model			
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-stat
C	4082.891***	755.487	5.404
ΔTEMP _t	-231.867	167.679	-1.383
ΔPREC _t	-197.688	127.254	-1.553
ΔCO2 _t	17.272***	4.745	3.640
ΔTEMP × PREC _t	42.61134	26.780	1.591
ΔTEMP × PREC _{t-1}	0.0309**	0.015	2.091
ΔPREC × CO2 _t	-1.037*	0.513	-2.020
ECT _{t-1}	-0.532***	0.099	-5.404
Long-Run Coefficients			
TEMP	-1654.375*	913.273	-1.811
PREC	-1269.348*	667.852	-1.901
CO2	59.773	37.179	1.608
TEMP × PREC	272.629*	142.474	1.914
TEMP × CO2	-3.770	6.181	-0.610
PREC × CO2	-6.374*	3.189	-1.999
Diagnostic Tests			
χ ² _{SER}	6.402 (0.006)	R ²	0.798
χ ² _{HET}	0.752 (0.681)	R ² _{Adj}	0.689
χ ² _{NORM}	0.816 (0.665)	F _{ist}	7.301 (0.000)
χ ² _{RAMSEY}	0.259 (0.615)	Cusum	Stable
DW	2.214	Cusum(sqr)	Stable

Note: See footnote from Table 4.

In light of the lack of cointegration, it is imperative to reformulate the model in first differences instead of persisting with the previously defined ECM. An ECM presupposes a stable, long-term relationship among the variables, relying on cointegration to model both short-term dynamics and adjustments toward a long-term equilibrium. In the absence of cointegration, this assumption becomes invalid, leading to the emergence of the following issues:

- In an ECM, the ECT is essential for quantifying the speed of adjustment back to equilibrium. In the absence of cointegration, a significant long-run equilibrium is unattainable, thereby rendering this term statistically invalid and its interpretation unsuitable.
- In the ECM, long-term coefficients delineate stable equilibrium relationships among variables. In the absence of cointegration, the interpretation of these coefficients would be erroneous, as they fail

to signify a stable long-term effect without a long-term relationship.

- Re-specifying the model in first differences facilitates an exclusive examination of short-run effects, precisely capturing the immediate influences of variations in the independent variables on yield growth. This method circumvents the presumption of non-existent equilibrium relationships, guaranteeing that the model accurately reflects only plausible short-term behaviors.

Employing a first-differenced model corresponds with the statistical characteristics of the data, guaranteeing consistency and robustness in estimating short-run relationships. This modification

facilitates an accurate and legitimate examination of immediate alterations in environmental variables and their effects on the yields, circumventing the errors of misinterpreting non-existent long-term stability.

In the modified model, we utilize an ARDL framework exclusively with differenced terms, thereby concentrating on short-run dynamics. This specification elucidated how fluctuations in CO₂ levels, precipitation, temperature, and their interactions directly influence pea yield growth. By examining solely the short-run coefficients, we circumvent dependence on a long-run relationship that the preliminary analysis suggested is absent. The findings are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Short-run results (pea)

Model: $F(\text{PEA}_t / \text{TEMP}_t, \text{PREC}_t, \text{CO}_2_t, \text{TEMP} \times \text{PREC}_t, \text{TEMP} \times \text{CO}_2_t, \text{PREC} \times \text{CO}_2_t)$			
Optimal Lag Length: (2, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)			
Short-Run Coefficients (Conditional ECM)			
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-stat
C	0.012	0.021	0.580
ΔPEA_{t-1}	-1.465***	0.257	-5.698
ΔTEMP_{t-1}	121.230	206.854	0.586
ΔPREC_t	-28.259	170.788	-0.165
ΔCO_2_t	40.050	48.337	0.829
$\Delta \text{TEMP} \times \text{PREC}_t$	5.557	35.732	0.156
$\Delta \text{TEMP} \times \text{CO}_2_t$	-7.852	9.066	-0.866
$\Delta \text{PREC} \times \text{CO}_2_t$	-0.006	0.630	-0.009
$\Delta(\Delta \text{PEA}_{t-1})$	0.277*	0.163	1.702
$\Delta(\Delta \text{TEMP}_t)$	115.185	207.392	0.555

Note: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $0.01 < p < 0.05$, * $0.05 < p < 0.10$.

The significant and negative coefficient of -1.465 for PEA_{t-1} suggests a strong negative effect of past yields on current yields. This implies that a high yield in the previous period is associated with a reduction in the current period's yield. This negative autocorrelation could indicate yield variability or cyclical patterns in pea production, possibly due to soil nutrient

depletion, pest cycles, or plant stress effects following a high-yield season.

TEMP does not show a statistically significant impact in the short run, indicating that temperature fluctuations do not have a strong immediate effect on pea yields. This suggests that peas may be relatively tolerant to short-term temperature variations within a certain range (Ogata et al., 1974). PREC is also non-significant,

suggesting that changes in rainfall do not immediately affect pea yields. This could imply that peas can tolerate moderate fluctuations in water availability or that short-term precipitation levels do not play a dominant role in their growth cycle (Maurer et al., 1968). Similar to TEMP and PREC, CO₂ does not show a significant impact, suggesting that short-term changes in atmospheric CO₂ concentrations may not have an immediate effect on pea yields in the short run.

None of the interaction terms between TEMP, PREC, and CO₂ are statistically significant. This implies that combinations of these environmental factors do not have a noticeable influence on pea yields in the short run, further supporting the notion that pea yields respond primarily to internal factors (such as past yields) rather than complex environmental interactions in the short term.

In sum, short-run dynamics show that previous yields (PEA_{t-1}) significantly influence current yields, with a negative effect that could suggest production lags or cyclical behavior in pea cultivation. Managing nutrient depletion or adjusting farming practices after high-yield seasons could help stabilize yields. Non-significant effects of TEMP, PREC, and CO₂ indicate that short-term environmental changes may not strongly impact pea yields. This could imply that peas are relatively stable in response to small environmental fluctuations in the immediate term.

Overall, the empirical findings from the ARDL analysis of barley yield indicate both long-run and short-run relationships with climatic variables. The presence of a stable long-term relationship (cointegration) is primarily due to barley's inherent physiological resilience. Barley typically demonstrates greater tolerance to climatic variability because it has deeper and more extensive root systems, allowing it to efficiently utilize available soil moisture

and withstand moderate temperature fluctuations over extended periods. Additionally, barley, as a C3 plant, benefits initially from elevated CO₂ levels due to enhanced photosynthetic rates. Over the long term, barley adjusts agronomically and physiologically to these gradual climatic shifts, maintaining equilibrium productivity. Therefore, sustained increases in temperature and precipitation provide stable conditions conducive to barley's growth, while the negative impact of prolonged elevated CO₂ exposure possibly reflects indirect stresses such as nutrient imbalance or resource constraints associated with high CO₂ concentrations.

In contrast, the ARDL analysis for pea yield reveals no long-term equilibrium relationship with the climatic variables studied, indicating that pea yields are sensitive primarily to short-term climatic fluctuations. Peas are characterized by shorter growth cycles and a more limited physiological tolerance to sudden environmental stresses such as extreme temperature spikes, sudden changes in moisture availability, or acute drought conditions. These transient environmental conditions disproportionately impact critical growth stages such as flowering, pod formation, and seed filling, resulting in immediate yield variability without persisting long-term effects. Consequently, understanding short-term dynamics is crucial because peas cannot readily adapt or stabilize yields through physiological adjustments across successive seasons. Short-term management practices, such as timing irrigation appropriately, implementing adaptive planting schedules, and employing practices to mitigate acute environmental stressors, thus become vital in stabilizing pea production.

4. Conclusion

This study offers a detailed examination of the effects of temperature, precipitation, and atmospheric CO₂ on the yields of two

crops in Turkiye: barley and peas. By applying the ARDL bounds testing approach with data from 1981 to 2020, we identified distinct responses among these crops to climatic variables, which carry implications for both short-term and long-term agricultural planning. Our analyses reveal that barley yields are cointegrated with climatic factors, indicating that temperature, precipitation, and CO₂ levels have a stable and lasting impact on its productivity over time. This long-term relationship suggests that barley yields in Turkiye have the capacity to adjust and maintain equilibrium in response to sustained changes in the environment, which may be beneficial for consistent productivity even under varying climatic conditions. The error correction term in the barley model showed a significant and rapid adjustment to deviations from this equilibrium, highlighting that barley production can quickly revert to stable output levels following short-term disruptions. This resilience implies that barley may be less vulnerable to immediate climatic fluctuations, making it a relatively reliable crop under changing environmental conditions. In contrast, the yield of peas does not exhibit cointegration with the climatic variables. This absence of a stable long-term relationship suggests that this do not adapt to ongoing environmental changes in the same way as barley. Instead, its yield is more sensitive to short-term climatic variations without forming a predictable, lasting pattern over time. For instance, temperature, precipitation, and CO₂ have immediate impacts on this crop, but their effects do not carry over in a stable manner, meaning that a good or poor yield in one season does not necessarily translate into similar outcomes in subsequent seasons. This transient response highlights the need for short-term adaptive management practices, such as adjusting irrigation or modifying planting schedules to buffer these crops against seasonal

variability and abrupt changes in climate conditions. The contrasting results between barley and peas underscore the importance of crop-specific management strategies. For barley, the identified stable long-term relationship with climatic variables underscores its relative resilience and highlights the potential effectiveness of long-term policies. Policymakers could support comprehensive soil health initiatives, such as encouraging farmers to adopt conservation tillage, crop rotation practices, and organic amendments to enhance soil organic matter and moisture retention. Additionally, nutrient management strategies tailored specifically for barley could be incentivized, including educational programs for farmers on optimal fertilizer application practices and investments in precision agriculture technologies. Encouraging research into drought-tolerant and heat-resistant barley varieties adapted specifically to Turkish agroecological conditions could further secure yield stability over prolonged periods. Conversely, pea yields exhibit sensitivity predominantly to short-term climate variability, emphasizing the importance of adaptive strategies that address immediate fluctuations. Practical implementation of these short-term strategies could include the promotion of adaptive irrigation management practices that rapidly respond to variability in rainfall, such as drip irrigation systems combined with real-time soil moisture sensors. Additionally, policymakers could support farmers in adopting protective agricultural techniques like temporary shading during heat waves or mulching practices that conserve moisture during drought periods. Effective dissemination of weather forecasts and early warning systems could also aid farmers in rapidly adjusting planting schedules and management decisions in response to anticipated extreme weather events, thus stabilizing pea yields from season to season.

In sum, this study provides valuable insights into the differential impacts of climatic variables on crop yields in Türkiye. Future research could build on these findings by exploring specific adaptive strategies, such as the development of drought-resistant crop varieties or the optimization of planting calendars. Additionally, incorporating more granular data on soil quality, pest pressures, and regional climatic patterns could further clarify how environmental interactions shape yield outcomes across diverse agricultural contexts in Türkiye. Such research would be instrumental in crafting evidence-based recommendations for farmers and policymakers alike, helping to secure sustainable food production in an era of increasing environmental uncertainty.

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